

DESIGNING A DIFFERENTIATED TRAINING IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING LEGAL SUBJECTS. (IN THE CASE OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION)

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Abstract. Education in the field of law for a teacher is the basic document for the planning of didactic games. Management plan of the traditional lesson plan differs focused and teachable students.

Keywords: planning, didactic games, interactive methods, "Cluster", "Gallery" technology "Hybrid", the legal culture.

In the professional education system, it is appropriate to use didactic games in the seminar classes of legal subjects. Because today it's no secret that seminar classes at academic lyceums are no different from lecture classes. A seminar is a form of training that directs the teacher to enter into an active conversation with the students, provides conditions for the implementation of theoretical knowledge in practical activities.

The effectiveness of the lesson depends on the thorough preparation and effective organization of the teacher. A lesson that is not well planned, not well thought out, hastily structured and not adapted to the capabilities of the students cannot be of high quality. It is to ensure that the preparation for the lesson is an educational process that ensures the achievement of the highest final result under certain conditions, and to develop complex measures and activities.

Lesson design (planning) is the creation of a program for managing students' educational activities, which is the final stage of preparation for the lesson. The project (management program) is short and clear, freely structured, the pedagogue defines for himself the important situations of the management process (from whom and when to speak, where to introduce the topic, how to move to the next stage of the training, according to which scheme to change the process in case of unforeseen difficulties). is a document that allows to receive A management program differs from a traditional lesson plan in that it clearly and clearly defines the effects [1,170-174 p.].

The design of didactic games for seminars in the teaching of legal sciences in the professional education system is as follows:

The purpose of the lesson:

- Introduction to the history of the origin of law;

- Creating skills about legal forms;
- Systematization of knowledge about legal fields;
- Providing information about legal knowledge, legal consciousness and legal culture. The design of didactic games for seminars in the teaching of legal sciences in the professional education system is as follows:

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Must know:

Basic concepts: legal culture, legal consciousness, legal knowledge, areas of law, legal state, history of law, crime.

1. *It should be understood:*

2. *The history of the formation of law;*

3. *The nature of legal forms;*

4. *Content of the legal fields;*

5. *It is necessary to understand the evolutionary stage of formation of legal knowledge, legal consciousness, legal culture.*

Applies to:

The skills of applying the knowledge acquired during the training process in life are formed and the will is strengthened.

Teaching methods: interactive methods, "Cluster", "Gallery" and "Hybrid" technology.

Form of education: work in teams.

Educational tools: game materials, textbook, notebook, colored felt-tip pen, felt-tip pen.

The progress of the lesson.

Preparation stage:

Teacher - determines the topic, prepares game materials, adapts the audience to the lesson, divides students into groups. "Lawyers", "Prosecutors", "Investigators", "Criminalists". Students are divided into groups and take their places.

Entry stage:

The teacher introduces the topic and plan, gives information about the purpose and task of the lesson. Gives a brief statement about the relevance of the topic.

The concept of legal culture is as important as other types of culture that a person should acquire in the process of formation as a "Person" in society. The state we are building is legal, and our society is a civil society. In such a country, laws prevail and citizens are equal.

We come across various situations, situations, and events in our society, we see cases of injustice and ask, "Why did this happen?" Who is to blame for this? This is unfair, isn't it?" by asking such questions, we feel compassion for the victim.

In fact, the victim himself is to blame for such a result! Due to the extremely low level of legal literacy, he is powerless to do anything because he does not have legal knowledge. He doesn't even know where to turn.

After the teacher finishes his short presentation, he gives information about the main concepts of the lesson. The "Cluster" method is used for this.

The main stage.

First stage:

"Gallery" technology - one question on the topic is distributed from tables divided into 4 groups. The representatives of the group write down answers to the questions and alternate places along the clock face. Answering the question of the second table, they move again. This situation continues until the team is in place.

Purpose:

- Strengthening and systematizing students' knowledge about the creation of rights.
- Motivating students mentally and physically during the lesson. Purpose:
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- Motivating students mentally and physically during the lesson.

Questions:

1. Psychological theory about the emergence of law;
2. Philosophical theory about the creation of law;
3. Historical theory about the emergence of law;
4. Sociological theory about the creation of law;
5. Realist theory about the creation of law;

Time: 3 minutes.

Order of answer:

Groups summarize the answers and present. A captain should be elected in the group, and all participants should participate in answering. As a result, all participants become active.

- Expected result:
- • Students engage in dialogue;
- • Thinks independently;
- • Expresses and defends his opinion;
- • Learns to think critically and challenge ideas..

Incentive: one incentive stick (colored counting sticks or other objects can be used as an incentive stick) is provided to the group that answered correctly. Иккинчи босқич.

"Hybrid" technology is a combination of interactive methods. Tasks are distributed to the groups, they complete the tasks within the specified time and make a presentation. "Presentation" means a presentation. In the process of presentation, students develop the skill of fluent delivery of their thoughts.

The first assignment.

"Cluster" method means to connect several options to each other, giving a solution to the problem. This method is aimed at teaching students to think logically, to expand the scope of common ideas, to use literature independently.

Question. Describe the forms of law in the three-step "Cluster" method.

- 1 - names of legal forms are written;
- 2 - defines the rules of legal forms;
- 3 - gives examples of legal forms.

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